

INFLUENCE OF CROSSLINK RATIO ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMERIC NANOCOMPOSITES AND INTERPHASE: A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION

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1 Introduction

Various types of polymeric nanocomposites have drawn huge attention due to their predisposed characteristics to alter the bulk properties of polymer. For example, as the size of particulates decreases to a nanometer scale, the contribution of interphase region on the nanocomposite turns out to be dominant, since the ratio of surface area to volume increases significantly. Thus the material properties of nanocomposites can be improved drastically, which is known as the particle size effects [1].

As far as the particle interfaces of nanocomposites are concerned, polymer mobility is of interest. The mobility of polymer can be influenced by the interaction of polymer chains with the nanoparticle surfaces [2]. Moreover, crosslinked networks, strong covalent bonds between polymer chains in thermoset polymer composites, can lead fundamental changes in polymer mobility. Thus the degree of crosslinking, known as crosslink ratio or crosslink density, is also important factor regarding polymer mobility [2, 3].

The interphase of thermoset polymer matrix-based nanocomposites can be influenced by embedded nanoparticles and crosslink ratios that alter the mobility of polymer matrix. Therefore, the characteristics of interphase, related with crosslink ratios and nanoparticulates, need to be rigorously considered when designing thermoset polymer nanocomposites.

In this study, the effect of different crosslink ratios and nanoparticle sizes on the mechanical properties of nanocomposites is investigated via molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and a sequential scale bridging method.

2 Molecular Dynamics Simulation Method

2.1 Representative Crosslinked Unit

Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol F (EPON862) is used as the epoxy monomer and Triethylenetetramine (TETA) is used as the curing agent. Crosslink ratio is defined as the ratio of the number of curing sites of TETA to the number of crosslinked sites. Crosslinked epoxy networks with different degrees of crosslink ratio, 25 %, 41.16 %, 50 % and 61.11 % are constructed while keeping the stoichiometric constant between EPON862 and TETA. MD simulation procedures in this study are conducted with the aid of Material Studio[®] 5.5, a commercial software program.

2.2 Silica/Epoxy Unit Cell

In total, 16 different unit cells are constructed. Firstly, pure epoxy unit cells are prepared, having different crosslink ratios that are listed in the previous section. Each cell consists of a number of representative crosslinked epoxy units to meet a proper cell size.

A spherical silica (SiO₂) particle, having the radius of 7.18 Å, 8.8 Å and 10.4 Å, is embedded at the center of an amorphous polymer matrix that has 4 different crosslink ratios. Each matrix of silica/epoxy unit cell is also consists of a number of representative crosslinked epoxy units, which is set to satisfy the same volume fraction, 5.8 % approximately.

The target density for pure epoxy and silica/epoxy unit cell is set to be 1.2 g/cm³ and periodic boundary conditions are applied to remove surface effects. *ab initio* Condensed-phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies (COMPASS) forcefield is applied to describe both inter and intramolecular interactions.

2.3 Elastic Modulus

The initial molecular structures are minimized using the conjugate gradient method. Then unit cells are equilibrated as follows. NVT ensemble at 300 K during 200 ps is followed by 2000 ps of NPT ensemble simulation at 300 K and 1 atm. The elastic modulus of each unit cell is obtained with the Parrinello-Rahman fluctuation method. At least, 12 repetitive simulations for the elastic modulus of each cell are conducted in order to enhance computational accuracy. The average values of modulus except the maximum and minimum value for each case are shown in Fig. 1.

3 Results

3.1 Effect of Particle Size and Crosslink Ratio

As the size of particles is decreased, the modulus of nanocomposites is increased under a fixed crosslink ratio as shown in Fig. 1. In the case of pure epoxy unit cells, elastic moduli show increasing tendency with respect to crosslink ratio. Derived modulus results are also in good agreement with the value of precedent surveys under same conditions.

3.2 Modulus Increment Ratio

It can be clearly found that the increment slope of modulus with respect to crosslink ratio is highly dependent to the size of nanoparticle. As is depicted in Fig. 2, the modulus slopes decrease as the particle size decreases since crosslinking reactions condense the matrix structure, disturbing to generate a stable

Fig. 1. Young's modulus with crosslink ratio for each particle radius

and stiff interphase zone between the matrix and the embedded nanoparticle.

4 Summary

The mechanical properties of various cases of Silica/Epoxy nanocomposites are investigated with the aid of MD simulations. A reinforcing effect on elastic moduli is observed as particle size decreases or crosslink ratio increases. In particular, the increasing amount of moduli is closely related with the ratio of surface area to volume of embedded nanoparticle which is the significant factor to elucidate interphase region.

References

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Fig. 2. The rate of modulus increase with crosslink ratio for each particle radius